

Double integrals in engineering mathematics: Confusing region geometry with integrands

Tracy S. Craig & Lerna Pehlivan

FERMAT (Fundamental Educational Research in Mathematics at Twente), Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Twente

Abstract

In engineering mathematics, double integrals are encountered in a wide range of fields, such as electrodynamics, aerodynamics and quantum mechanics. Setting up appropriate bounds and integrands is key to successfully solving an integral; computation is often easy, by hand or with software. In a recent study within a multivariable calculus course for Electrical Engineering, Applied Physics and Advanced Technology majors, we investigated students' proficiency at setting up double integrals to represent the area of a two-dimensional region provided in a diagram. In the case of computing an area, the integrand should be unity, yet we found that a significant portion of the students created an integrand out of the bounds of the region. One identical error was incurred by sixty percent of those cases. In this paper we present the different classes of incorrect integrands, how students relate to the geometry of the region and discuss potential causes. In particular, we observe that when using a single variable to calculate area under a curve, the integrand is not unity, which might cause cognitive conflict. We discuss implications for the teaching and learning of double integrals and suggest educational interventions.

Introduction

Integral calculus, both single and multivariable, is a very important subject for engineers and physicists, with many applications (Martínez-Planell & Trigueros, 2020). It is important that engineering students receive a good grounding in how to construct and to solve integrals in their mathematics classes, so that they can then use these mathematical tools confidently and with proficiency in their technical and disciplinary contexts. We have observed, and studies in this area have confirmed, that students struggle with interpreting integrals and their definitions.

Multiple studies investigating students' conceptual understanding of single variable definite integrals reveal that students heavily lean towards describing definite integrals in terms of area (Jones, 2013; Gemechu, Mogiso, Hussein and Adugna, 2021). In fact, there is a strong prototype image employed when describing definite integrals. This image is of a continuous function in the first quadrant displaying certain characteristics such as not varying far from its average value (Jones, 2018). Furthermore, studies show that students struggle to make sense of the (non-geometric) definition of the definite integral, the Riemann sum (Wagner, 2018). Since the definite integral is defined as the limit of a Riemann sum and not as an image of an area, the predominance of an area conception over a Riemann sum conception is troubling.

Certainly there is a link between geometry and integration (Martínez-Planell & Trigueros, 2021; Milenković, Božić & Takači, 2023). Bašić and Milin Šipuš (2022) describe the link as an "intricate connection" (p. 251) and Milenković, Božić and Takači (2023) have found

correlations between proficiency at analytical geometry and that of integral calculus. Jones (2018) argues that prototype images can be useful but also have drawbacks such as raising assumptions that a mathematical object will always display certain properties.

Studies into students' conceptions of the double integral find that these conceptions are linked to those the students already have of the single variable definite integral (Jones and Dorko, 2015; Özbey & Dost, 2023). Since area is the predominant single variable integral conception, this link translates to strongly area-correlated conceptions of double integrals. Jones and Dorko (2015) identify ten conceptions of the double integral of a function on a region, of which several are correct and related to area; for example, "double integral as adding up slices". In contrast to these correct conceptions, however, they do find a certain subset of their cohort interpreting $\int_R f(x, y) dA$ as area of a region in the (normatively incorrect) understanding they call "the double integral as boundary and area".

Similar to their single variable counterparts, double integrals are defined in terms of a Riemann sum. Studies have shown that typical textbook treatments of the double integral Riemann sum tend to be less fully presented than that of the single variable Riemann sum, suggesting (against evidence) that students can transfer their understanding from one to the other (McGee and Martínez-Planell, 2014). Martínez-Planell, and Trigueros (2020) find that many students are confused by elements of the Riemann sum construction and struggle to relate the Riemann sum as a whole with the double integral. In the study of Özbey and Dost (2023) they investigated pre-service mathematics teachers' conceptions of double integrals. They find that students struggled to construct double integrals to describe area unless "the function" was given, some students did not recognise "1" as a function, and others who knew that the integrand should be 1 struggled to explain why.

With the exception of some studies such as Özbey and Dost's, in which students were asked to construct integrals, most educational studies of integrals involve presenting students with already constructed integrals and asking for interpretations. Our study differed from that general trend, in that we presented students with a diagram of a region and requested construction of the double integral for area. Given the studies showing the strong link between the symbolic integral and the geometric idea of area, the exercise is apparently well aligned with students' conceptions of integration. Instead of seeing apparent alignment between our exercise and students' conceptions of integral as area, we found that a significant minority of the cohort provided integrands that were either related to the geometry of the region or were at best conditionally correct. Our study contributes to the field by presenting results related to students' conception of integral-as-area in an unconventional form, that is calling for construction of area double integrals. The results we discuss here and elsewhere (Craig & Pehlivan, 2025) respond to the call for more studies into the teaching and learning of multivariable calculus (Martínez-Planell & Trigueros, 2021).

Research Methodology

We carried out a study investigating students' construction of bounds of double integrals representing area of a lamina (Craig & Pehlivan, 2025). The focus of the mentioned study is the bounds of integration. However, one phenomenon apparent in the data was the tendency of some students to express the integrand in terms of one or more of the bounds of the region. It is this phenomenon on which we focus in this paper. Data were collected in a standard calculus exam offered to students in the programmes of electrical engineering, advanced technology and applied physics at a technical university in the Netherlands. 168 students wrote the exam and the exercise on which data was collected can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Exam exercise on double integrals

Correct answers to the exercise in Figure 1 are

- $\int_8^{18} \int_1^{\sqrt{x/2}} 1 dy dx$,
- $\int_1^2 \int_8^{18} 1 dx dy + \int_2^3 \int_{2y^2}^{18} 1 dx dy$.

Each student's answer was recorded in typed form and the data were anonymised. Each record included bounds of integration and the integrand.

Integrands chosen by the students were divided into three categories, namely correct, conditionally correct and incorrect. Correct integrands included writing the number 1 explicitly, or leaving it out entirely. Conditionally correct integrands were $f(x)$ and $f(x, y)$ since these are correct under the condition that $f(x) = 1$ or $f(x, y) = 1$. Any other integrand was incorrect, with the majority of those being related in some way to the geometry of the region.

Data Analysis

In part (a) (see Table 1), of the total 168 students, 104 provided the correct integrand. A further 32 gave an integrand that was conditionally correct. 17 out of 32 wrote $f(x, y)$ for the integrand while the remaining 15 used $f(x)$ as the integrand. 25 students used the region itself to contrive an integrand, the most common integrand being $2y^2$, provided by 15 students. Two students gave incorrect integrands unrelated to the region.

Integrand	Count (% of 168)	Subcounts [frequency]
Correct	104 (63%)	
Conditionally correct	32 (19%)	$f(x, y)$ [17], $f(x)$ [15]
Related to the region	25 (15%)	$2y^2$ [15], $\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}$ [3], R [3], $2y^2 - x$ [2], $18 - 2y^2$ [1], $2y^2 - 1$ [1]
Other	2 (1%)	x [1], y [1]
Omitted the exercise	5 (3%)	

Table 1. Integrand categories in student responses to part (a)

In part (b) (see Table 2) 102 students provided the correct integrand. 29 students provided conditionally correct integrands. 16 of them chose $f(x, y)$ as the integrand and the remaining 13 chose $f(x)$. 28 students provided integrands that were either clearly or apparently derived from the region itself. The most common of these was $\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}$ provided by 12 students.

Integrand	Count (% of 168)	Subcounts [frequency]
Correct	102 (61%)	
Conditionally correct	29 (17%)	$f(x, y)$ [16], $f(x)$ [13]
Related to the region	28 (17%)	$\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}$ [12], $2y^2$ [6], $2y^2 - x$ [2], R [2], $2y^2x$ [1], $\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}} - y$ [1], $x - 2y^2$ [1], 8 [1], $\frac{x}{4}$ [1], $\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{x}$ [1]
Omitted the exercise	9 (5%)	

Table 2. Integrand categories in student responses to part (b)

We note that, if we were to express the area of the region as single variable integrals, correct answers for (a) and (b) would be

$$(a) \int_8^{18} \left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}} - 1 \right) dx \text{ and } (b) \int_1^2 (18 - 8)dy + \int_2^3 (18 - 2y^2)dy.$$

No student provided an integrand of $\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}} - 1 \right)$ for either (a) or (b), although three did provide $\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}$ in part (a). One student provided an integrand of $(18 - 2y^2)$ for part (a), but none did for part (b).

Discussion of findings

In this paper we are primarily interested in students' incorrect integrands. However, it is notable that conditionally correct integrands are slightly more prevalent in the data set. We are reminded of Özbey and Dost's (2023) findings that some of their students' belief that an integral cannot be constructed without "the function" and that 1 is not a function.

Introductory calculus textbooks typically begin defining integration as area under a curve (Adams & Essex, 2021). A graph of a function $f(x) > 0$ is typically depicted, over a closed interval, and the area is approximated by a sum of rectangle areas. By allowing the number of rectangles to tend to infinity and the width of the rectangles to become infinitesimally small, the "true" area under the curve is represented by the limit of a Riemann sum. The height of the rectangles becomes the integrand of the integral. Thus, from the very beginning of the topic of integration, (single variable) integrals are introduced as representing area, with the integrand being the function "under which" is the area in question.

Similarly, when double integrals are first introduced, they are typically introduced very visually, as volume under a surface. Little tiles are defined in the xy -plane, with the value of the function $f(x, y) > 0$ providing the height of the rectangular prisms under the surface. The sum of the volumes of the prisms is an approximation of the volume under the surface and, in the limit, becomes the double integral of the function.

Once double integrals are defined in terms of volume under a surface, as teachers we can expand beyond that definition to interpret, for example, $\iint_R \sigma(x, y) dA$ as mass of a lamina, if $\sigma(x, y)$ is area density, and $\iint_R dA$ as area of a lamina, given that this integral represents the limit of a sum of tiles of area ΔA .

We make two observations that we argue are influential factors. First, we teach the various types of Riemann integration in the order single variable, double, triple, line and surface. In all but single variable integration, we teach an interpretation of the integral where the integrand is 1. That is, area of a lamina, volume of a solid, length of a curve, and area of a surface. In single variable integration, however, the nature of $\int_a^b 1 dx$ is usually not addressed. Thus, an integrand of 1 is first encountered in double integrals, with no prior similar construction to build upon cognitively. Our second observation is that double integral as volume is often framed as the simplest interpretation of a double integral. "In the simplest instance, the volume of a three-dimensional region is given by a double integral of its height over the two-dimensional plane region that is its base" (Adams and Essex, 2021, p. 833). We suggest that "double integral as volume" is not the simplest interpretation of a double integral, but that area of a two-dimensional region is.

Conclusions

Our study investigated students' conceptual understanding of constructing double integrals for area. We observed that a number of students, albeit a minority, placed a geometric feature of the region in the integrand instead of the correct integrand of 1. We

suggest that this error is rooted in the students' understanding of the single variable integral $\int_a^b f(x)dx$ representing area under a curve.

We make three suggestions for teaching.

1. When teaching single variable integration, associate $\int_a^b 1dx$ with the length of $[a, b]$.
2. When introducing double integrals, instead of beginning with an integrand of $f(x, y)$ and an interpretation of the result as volume, begin with an integrand of 1 and an interpretation as area. Thereafter a variety of integrands can be introduced, all with their interpretations (for example volume or mass) equally weighted in importance.
3. When teaching double integral for area, be explicit that the earlier definition of single variable as area is, in effect, a double integral with the first computational step already carried out. That is

$$\int_a^b \int_0^{f(x)} 1dy dx = \int_a^b f(x)dx$$

A limitation of the study, as pertains to the results discussed here, is that the study only recorded the double integral constructions for area double integrals. No other types of integrals were addressed and there were no interviews. To further investigate the construction of integrands, a follow up study could include construction of a variety of types of integrals, or area integrals for a variety of different shaped regions. Additionally, interviews would increase clarity.

References

- Adams, R. A., & Essex, C. (2021). *Calculus a complete course*. Pearson.
- Bašić, M., & Milin Šipuš, Ž. (2022). Geometrical reasoning in the teaching and learning of integrals of multivariable functions. *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, 8(2), 245-268.
- Craig, T.S. & Pehlivan, L. (2025 forthcoming). Students' conceptions of double integral bounds: An APOS Theory perspective. Meanjin Delta 2025, Brisbane November 2025.
- Gemechu, E., Mogiso, A., Hussein, Y., & Adugna, G. (2021). Students' conception on multiple integrals of a function of several variables: A case of Adama Science and Technology University. *American Journal of Applied Mathematics*, 9(1), 10-15.
- Jones, S. R. (2013). Understanding the integral: Students' symbolic forms. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 32(2), 122-141.
- Jones, S. R. (2018). Prototype images in mathematics education: The case of the graphical representation of the definite integral. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 97(3), 215-234.
- Jones, S. R., & Dorko, A. (2015). Students' understandings of multivariate integrals and how they may be generalized from single integral conceptions. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 40, 154-170.

- Martínez-Planell, R., & Trigueros, M. (2020). Students' understanding of Riemann sums for integrals of functions of two variables. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 59, 100791.
- Martínez-Planell, R., & Trigueros, M. (2021). Multivariable calculus results in different countries. *ZDM–Mathematics Education*, 53, 695-707.
- McGee, D. L., & Martínez-Planell, R. (2014). A study of semiotic registers in the development of the definite integral of functions of two and three variables. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 12, 883-916.
- Milenković, A., Božić, R., & Takači, Đ. (2023). Correlation analysis of students' success in solving analytic geometry and multiple integral problems. *The Teaching of Mathematics*, XXVI, 2, 88-105.
- Özbey, M., & Dost, Ş. (2023). Concept images of prospective mathematics teachers for geometric representation of the double integral concept. *Necatibey Faculty of Education Electronic Journal of Science & Mathematics Education*, 17(1), 66-98.
- Wagner, J. F. (2018). Students' obstacles to using Riemann sum interpretations of the definite integral. *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, 4, 327-356.